

“Falsafa va hayot” xalqaro jurnal
“Философия и жизнь” международный журнал
“Philosophy and Life” International journal

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**ТА’ЛИМ ВА ФАН ФАЛСАФАСИ /
ФИЛОСОФИЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И НАУКИ /
PHILOSOPHY OF EDUCATION AND SCIENCE**

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FALSAFIY TA’LIMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLARI

Annotatsiya. Falsafiy ta’limning maqsadi pedagogikada qo’llaniladigan har bir yondashuv asosida turuvchi falsafiy bilimlarning mazmun-mohiyatini hamda ularning muayyan turdagi ta’limni ishlab chiqish maqsadlariga muvofiq ekanligini aniqlash bilan xarakterlanadi. Falsafiy ta’limning ushbu maqsadini ontologik yondashuv hamda tadqiqotning tizimli-tahliliy usuliga asoslangan holda amalga oshirish mumkin. Falsafiy ta’lim doirasida olib borilgan maxsus tadqiqotlar natijasida ishlab chiqilgan falsafiy bilimlar tizimi o’quv jarayonini falsafa, turli fanlar, din, san’atning nazariy va amaliy asoslariga tayangan holda tuzish imkonini beradi. Shuningdek, falsafiy ta’lim qonuniyatlari va tarkibiy tuzilmasi murakkablashib borishini ham alohida qayd etishimiz lozim.

Kalit so’zlar: ta’lim, falsafa, bilim, borliq, amaliyot, nazariya, qonuniyat, faoliyat, fan, taraqqiyot, taraqqiyot.

**ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ФИЛОСОФСКОГО
ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ**

Аннотация. Цель философского образования характеризуется его соответствием сущности философских знаний, лежащих в основе каждого подхода, используемого в педагогике, и их целям развития конкретного вида образования. Эта цель философского образования может быть реализована на основе онтологического подхода и системно-аналитического метода исследования. Система философских знаний, выработанная в результате специальных исследований, проводимых в рамках философского образования, позволяет строить образовательный процесс на основе теоретических и практических основ философии, различных наук, религии и искусства. Следует также отметить, что закономерности и структурная структура философского образования усложняются.

Ключевые слова: образование, философия, знание, бытие, практика, теория, право, деятельность, наука, прогресс.

PERSPECTIVES OF DEVELOPING THE PHILOSOPHICAL EDUCATION

Annotation. The purpose of philosophical education is characterized by its compliance to the essence of the philosophical knowledge underlying each approach used in pedagogy and their goals for the development of a specific type of education. This goal of philosophical education can be realized based on an ontological approach and a systematic-analytical method of research. The system of philosophical knowledge, developed as a result of special researches conducted within the framework of philosophical education, makes it possible to structure the educational process based on the theoretical and practical foundations of philosophy, various sciences, religion, and art. We should also note that the laws and structural structure of philosophical education are becoming more complex.

Keywords: education, philosophy, knowledge, existence, practice, theory, law, activity, science, progress.

INTRODUCTION

The peculiar feature of the global education market is that it is a very competitive environment. First, education is becoming more and more a means of entering the globalized labor and latest technology markets, and secondly, it is becoming an important element of the state's economic strategy in capturing new markets. The level of education of the population of Uzbekistan determines the level of its competitiveness in the world market. The stable development of the education sector is the guarantee of ensuring rapid socio-economic development of our country. In order to achieve it, it is important to ensure the effective operation of higher education institutions based on the improvement of economic relations in the market of educational services.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The article uses induction, deduction, systematic and comparative analysis, sociological survey methods, and the principles of historicity and logic.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

History testifies that man discovered the universe for himself, determined his position in it, learned to see the future (contours) and, taking into account past experience, tried to change today (present day). For man, this "climbing the ladder of time" was not easy and without obstacles. At the same time, as recognized by many, the path of man from the stone ax to the creation of the modern computer is a clear proof that the improvement of human thinking knows no limits [1].

Emphasizing the importance of education, in particular, the higher education system, in the development of society, the following need to be studied as factors for improving the quality and efficiency of education, they are as follows:

- paying special attention to the socialization of young people in the context of globalization;

- to positively solve the issue of smooth transition to the modernized education system in the conditions of the market economy by improving the available opportunities;

- analysis of the social and economic aspects of ensuring the effectiveness of the improvement of the philosophical education system in the higher education system;

- scientific substantiation that the development of education in the higher education system has been improved in accordance with the tasks set in the "National Personnel Training Program";

- theory and practice in philosophical education, research on increasing its effectiveness and creation of a mathematical model of a differentiated payment contract;

- to determine the interrelationship between philosophical education and the pursuit of effective education.

"Education is a means of socialization and serves to form the personality of a person, which ensures the internal balance of society. "Education manifests itself in the formation of stable values and confidence in one's capabilities in a person's source of wide knowledge, and the ability to widely use these capabilities in life activities and civil society"[2].

In the current period, it is required to use a new methodology, that is, to use innovative methods, in the teaching of philosophy, as in the teaching of all subjects. That is, the need for us to work on the problems of teaching our national philosophy on the basis of a new methodology, the formation of which has not yet been completed, is becoming indirect. Based on these conditions, it can be seen how difficult it is to teach philosophy in educational institutions today. Accordingly, becoming an expert in philosophy is extremely difficult, and at the same time, a very honorable and responsible job. But this honor is only the conscience of the teacher and some students who understand it, it is an indiscriminate honor that is not felt by others. In order to get this honor, it is important that we first have a general idea about the learning process.

"Philosophical education represents a specific form of philosophical activity in the field of education. The very concept of education needs to be clarified. The goal of such philosophical activity is to perceive a more perfect view of education, as well as its development, interpretation, and wide application in practice at all social levels. In the process of such a philosophical analysis, the category of "education" itself is understood as a process of continuous development and renewal [3].

Different views on the essence of philosophical education should not be considered as opposites, but as views reflecting different levels and aspects of philosophical knowledge. In this case, only philosophical education, as a department of philosophy, can claim the full implementation of all tasks of theoretical knowledge - both knowledge acquisition (descriptive, explanatory and predictive) and technological (projective, organizational, reflexive-corrective).

Determining the content of the essence of philosophical education can be done on the basis of studying the features of its relationship with pedagogy.

"The change, enrichment, expansion, and diversity of the quantitative and qualitative aspects of human thinking and consciousness depend, first of all, on social experience, and secondly, on the characteristics of the human personality and individual ability"[4].

The philosophy of education should first of all help to understand the essence of the subject of pedagogy, in which the immutable structure of its content can be determined by the qualitative characteristics of this subject, which are particularly emphasized at the modern stage of the development of pedagogy.

When determining the main features of the science of pedagogy, unlike the previous situation, it is necessary to take into account the things that clearly express the modern type of education and clearly define it. In the 20th century, two main types of education were distinguished. In 1974, in the report of the scientists of the Club of Rome called "Education has no borders", these types of education were called supportive and innovative types of education [5]. The past decades made it possible to determine the characteristics of the main types of education.

Philosophy embodies new achievements in various branches of knowledge through the concepts of extremely relevant worldviews. And pedagogy, in turn, manifests the advanced methods of education and training and through this forms the inner world of the growing generation. Also, an objective attitude to changes in society plays an important role in ensuring tolerance among people. The development of philosophical education, in turn, is formed at a high level through youth activity.

The first type of education is focused on human formation, and the second type can be defined as education focused on human development. The first is usually described as traditional or authoritarian education. When it comes to the second type of education, it is seen as education that is still in the process of being formed. In this case, the need to solve the problem of the invariant structure of the content of philosophy is especially growing.

In the first type of education, the main tasks of the pedagogical process are delivery (by the pedagogue) and acquisition (by the student). In this case, the factor selected in advance with the help of social experience and defined as important from the pedagogical point of view is of great importance in the construction of the educational process. In this regard, the social experience assessed as necessary by the state, society, or individual is distinguished. Then, the mastery of this content is considered as the main goal. In pedagogy, this model of education is described as knowledge acquisition. The function of human development in this model is secondary. For the second type, the task of human development remains as a leader in general. This means that the goal of education is related to human development, it should be based on the study of naturally occurring qualities in the process of educating and educating a person at all stages of human development. In this case, the content of education plays this role as the main pedagogical tool. At each stage

of this process, however, each feature of the stages of human development is chosen according to its goals, and can also be variable.

In our opinion, quality indicators of education focused on human development should serve as the basis for creating the structure of modern educational philosophy. At the same time, the philosophy of education must include a historical part that reflects the philosophical foundations of various models of education. Because, with the help of the historical basis, it is possible to solve the research tasks on the construction of modern educational models. For example, it is possible to determine the trend of changes in the quality characteristics of the educational process, or to find new ways of using philosophical ideas that are already embodied in pedagogical practice.

CONCLUSION

Philosophical education is one of the directions of the field of education, which has a complex nature in the educational process. Because the essence of philosophical education is important with a perfect reflection of the issue being covered. In the modern paradigm of philosophical education, the teacher and the student are considered subjects of the pedagogical process. But, at the same time, the leadership role of the teacher is preserved. This places a special responsibility on the teacher to constantly search for himself, improve his professional skills, and constantly improve his knowledge. Another important aspect is the progressive function of the development of the educational system in modern society. It will have priority in the social sphere as an actual factor of collectiveness. This, in turn, is expressed by the important role of the development of the educational system in the information society of a new scale. At the same time, philosophical education incorporates national educational models.

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